

Current mismatch reduction in charge pumps using regulated current stealing-injecting transistors for PLLs

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ABSTRACT

A charge pump for phase locked loops (PLL) with a novel current mismatch compensation technique is proposed. The proposed circuit uses a simple yet effective current stealing-injecting (CSI) technique and feedback to reduce mismatch between the negative-channel-metal-oxide (NMOS) and positive-channel-metal-oxide (PMOS) transistors. The current stealing transistor steals the current from a replica branch and mirrors it to the output where it is added to the output branch by the injecting transistor. A feedback mechanism is used to set the drain voltages of both branches to be equal and mitigate channel length modulation and ensure high accuracy. The proposed circuit was designed on Silterra 130nm technology and simulated using Cadence Spectre. The simulation results show that the proposed circuit yields a maximum of 0.107% and minimum of 0.00465% current mismatch while operating at a low supply voltage of 800mV for a range of 100mV to 700mV. The proposed design uses only one rail-to-rail op amp for compensating the mismatch and an addition of 4 transistors and utilizing 75% of the supply voltage for high voltage controlled oscillator (VCO) tuning range.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been an increasing demand for continuous supply of integrated circuits or better known as chips, for various purposes, the most recent and prevalent applications being 5G wireless chips and processors. One common block in these chips is the phase locked loops (PLL). The motivation of this work is to build one of the most important building blocks in a PLL system, namely, the charge pump. As mentioned earlier, the PLL has seen usage in chips, specifically serializes and deserializes (SERDES) protocols and radio frequency (RF) transceiver systems. In SERDES protocols, the PLL in the transmitter chain is responsible for the timing functionality [1]-[3]. Meanwhile, in RF transceivers, the PLL is used for the up-conversion and down-conversion of the signal through the mixer [4]-[6]. Apart from that, PLLs can also be used as frequency multipliers in microcontrollers, autonomous batteryless circuits [7] and as a clock generator in wireless sensor nodes (WSN) for health monitoring systems [8].

This work highlights the research problem with the charge pump in the PLL that can disrupt the PLL operation due to the current mismatch of the up current carried by the positive-channel-metal-oxide (PMOS) and down current carried by the negative-channel-metal-oxide (NMOS). Specifically, the current mismatch

VCO. The works by [15]-[17] employ digital calibration techniques to calibrate the charge pump mismatch. The typical blocks involved include a lock detector (LD), some form of phase detector, a digitally-controlled charge pump and calibration circuitry. The calibration circuitry can be in the form of digital-to-analog converter (DAC), filter and digital logics, as is the case in [15] or even successive-approximate register (SAR) based logic [16]-[17] and controls the digitally-controlled charge pump calibration process. The idea is basically the same, that is, the LD functions to detect whether the PLL has been locked and signals the start of calibration. The phase detector, either bang bang phase detector (BBPD) [15]-[16] or high resolution phase detector (HRPD) [17], functions to detect the difference of phase between the reference frequency and the feedback frequency. HRPD is an improvement of the BBPD proposed by [17] and is superior in terms of accuracy.

2.2. Analog-centric techniques

Other more traditional approaches are more analog centric in the way that they employ negative feedback loops and replica bias techniques to handle the current mismatch [19]-[24]. Some of these techniques are viable only due to the abundance of voltage headroom while others are inherently complex in terms of design implementation, that is they require additional circuitry for current compensation. For example, Figure 2(a) shows the charge pump architecture by [18] in which a cascode structure was used. Since the transistors need to be in saturation region, the V_{DS} of each stacked transistor must be high, hence the output voltage, V_{ctrl} is limited to a range of roughly $2V_{DSn}$ to $V_{DD} - 2V_{SDp}$. On top of that, this technique is only viable when there is ample headroom for the transistors to saturate and is not suitable for low voltage design.

With regards to complexity, while the mentioned works use the concept of negative feedback, the key here is to use as fewer components as possible for implementing the compensation schemes. As an example, Figure 2(b) shows the charge pump design proposed by [19] in which a lot of extra circuitry was added in order to compensate the current mismatch such as 3 op amps, capacitors and resistors. Other than that, the work by [20] uses 1 rail to rail op amp while also adding extra circuitry for current compensation and mismatch cancellation. Hwang *et al.* [21] use 2 op amps in a dual feedback loop to compensate the current mismatch. On the other hand, Lozada and Espinosa [23] designed a fully differential charge pump which requires double the normal circuitry to operate. A bulk-driven charge pump in triple well technology was proposed by [24] which uses 1 op amp with the addition of several transistors and also resistors.

Figure 2. Examples of charge pump architectures; (a) A cascode charge pump design by [18], (b) A charge pump design by [19] utilizing 3 op amps as the compensation scheme

2.3. Low voltage techniques

The recent trend of CP design is moving towards low supply voltage architectures. Some of the recent CP circuit design techniques that have been employed for low voltage operation include gate switching CP [25]-[26], DTMOS transistors for leakage control [27], diode-connected MOS CP [28], non-cascode source-switch CP [29], clock-gated CP with tunable low pass filter (LPF) [30] and dual feedback loop CP [31].

From the literature survey, it can be concluded that there is room for improvement in terms of the complexity of the architecture used in order to compensate the current mismatch. It can be seen that previous

Table 1. Device sizing for the proposed charge pump design

Device	Size	Device	Size
MP1	30u/1u, m=2	MN2	4u/130n
MP2	30u/1u, m=2	MN3	20u/1u, m=4
MP3	30u/1u, m=2	MN4	20u/1u, m=4
MP4	30u/1u, m=2	MN5	20u/1u, m=8
MP5	30u/1u, m=2	MN6	10u/1u, m=4
MP6	30u/1u, m=2	MN7	10u/1u, m=4
MP7	30u/1u, m=2	MN8	4u/130n
MN1	4u/130n	MN9	4u/130n

The opposite happens when the UP signal is low and DN is high. In order to ensure wide compliance range of the charge pump, a rail to rail input op amp must be used. This work uses a rail-to-rail amp by [32] for constant-gm operation. The op amp used in this design uses a common drain input stage as a DC level shifter to shift the input voltages down and ensure constant-gm operation, followed by a common source stage. The input stage is followed by a current summing stage and a folded cascode load. A push-pull configuration was used for the output stage with miller compensation. The op amp design is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The rail-to-rail input op amp with common drain input stage as DC level shifter for constant-gm operation [32]

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A pre-layout SPICE simulation was done using Cadence Spectre EDA tool to verify the effectiveness of the proposed technique in reducing the current mismatch in the charge pump. The simulation environment is under typical transistor conditions at a temperature of 27°. Figure 5(a) shows the drain current that is drawn by transistors at the output branch, namely MP3, MN3, MN6 and the net current. As explained previously, the drain current of MP3 carries 100µA, while MN3 carries 50µA. The drain current of MN6 is mirrored from MN7 and it tracks the difference of current between the MP4 and MN4, which ideally is 50µA. The drain current of MN6 is injected to the output node A to compensate for the mismatch. The net output current is given by the sum of the drain currents of MP3, MN3 and MN6. As depicted, it can be seen that the net output current is relatively constant in the 0µ regime, signifying that the output current mismatch is minimized.

Figure 5(b) shows the comparison of current mismatch with and without the current stealing-injecting and feedback technique. For the conventional charge pump, it can be seen that the current mismatch varies greatly when the Vctrl is varied from 0V to 0.8V, achieving up to an absolute current mismatch of 26µA or 26% across the range of 100mV to 700mV. In contrast, the proposed charge pump circuit is relatively constant with an absolute maximum and minimum current mismatch of only 107 nA or 0.107% and 4.65 nA or 0.00465% respectively for the same range with 75% utilization of the headroom. The stark contrast between the current mismatch of the proposed and the conventional charge pump is a testament to the effectiveness in reducing the current mismatch in charge pumps. On top of that, the proposed circuit guarantees a mismatch of less than 1% from 31mV to 737mV which is 87.5% of the available headroom. From the Figure 5, it can also be noticed that when Vctrl approaches the upper and lower supply rails, the current mismatch deteriorates as the transistors MP3, MP4 and MN3 and MN4 will go into the linear region.

Figure 5. The current mismatch simulation results; (a) Drain current of transistors at the output branch, (b) Current mismatch when V_{ctrl} is varied from 0 to 0.8V

In order to ensure the proposed circuit is not oscillating, the stability of the negative feedback loop in the charge pump design is analyzed. Figure 5(a) shows the gain and phase margin of the proposed charge pump over the input V_{ctrl} range of 100mV to 700mV. As can be seen, the achieved gain is from 79.58 dB to 112.23 dB. The phase margin range is from 57.8° to 68.9° indicating that the design is stable since it is within the vicinity of 60° . A Monte Carlo statistical simulation is carried out to verify under process variation, namely the (μC_{ox}) and (V_{th}). By running the Monte Carlo simulation, the extent of process variation on the current mismatch can be gauged. The Monte Carlo was run using Cadence Spectre tool with the confidential model files as the input given by the foundry, which cannot be disclosed. Figure 6(b) shows the Monte Carlo simulation of the proposed charge pump.

Figure 6. Stability and Monte Carlo simulation results; (a) The gain and phase margin of the negative feedback loop in the proposed charge pump design, (b) Statistical Monte Carlo simulation for current mismatch with 200 runs

The design achieved an absolute maximum current mismatch with a mean of 107.4nA and standard deviation of 1.76nA, proving that it is a robust design over global and local variations. It can be seen that although subjected to process variation, the Monte Carlo simulation shows that the mismatch closely agrees with the pre-layout simulation under typical conditions. Table 2 summarizes the performance of the proposed CSI relative to previous works in charge pump design. From the table, it can be seen that the proposed design has the lowest current mismatch among all other works reported in literature. The calculation of the percentage of utilization is $(High\ boundary - Low\ boundary)/VDD * 100\%$. In the proposed design, the high boundary

is 700mV while the low boundary of the 100mV. The boundaries are taken at 100mV from the supply voltage (800mV) and ground (0V) to ensure the transistors at the output and replica branch have sufficient V_{DS} to operate in saturation. With a supply voltage (VDD) of 800mV, the proposed charge pump yields a percentage of utilization of 75%. On top of that, the design operates at a supply voltage of 800mV, which is the lowest among all the other works and still manage to achieve 75% utilization, on par with or better than other works. This superior current mismatch performance will enable it to minimize the effects of spur on the PLL and ensure spectral purity.

Table 2. Comparison of previous works in charge pump design

	This Work	[20]	[21]	[22]	[23]	[24]	[25]
Technology (nm)	130	180	65	130	65	180	180
Supply Voltage (V)	0.8	3	1.0	1.2	1.1	1.8	1.2
Vctrl Range (V)	0.1-0.7	0.2-2.7	0.1-0.85	0.2-1	0.1-0.92	0.3-1.5	0.2-1
Absolute Current Mismatch (%)	0.005-0.1	2.1	0.023-0.432	3.2	0.05	0.32	0.9
Up/Down Current (μA)	100	600	150	100	1000	100	140
Percentage of Utilization (%)	75	83.33	75	66.67	74.5	66.67	66.67
Standard Deviation (%)	<0.02	NA	<0.03	1.7	<2	<3.5	NA

5. CONCLUSION

A novel charge pump utilizing the CSI technique and feedback was designed to minimize the current mismatch which is important to reduce spur which will deteriorate the spectral purity of the PLL. The proposed charge pump uses only 1 rail to rail op amp in addition to 4 more transistors for the compensation scheme, which is low in complexity, resulting in high accuracy and minimal mismatch. Pre-layout SPICE simulation results using Cadence Spectre EDA tool show significant improvement over existing architectures in literature in terms of current mismatch, achieving a maximum and minimum mismatch of 0.107% and 0.00465% respectively at 800 mV supply voltage from a range of 100mV to 700mV. The design is also robust across process variations and is suitable for low voltage applications. In the future, the layout for the charge pump will be design for silicon fabrication. On top of that, the proposed charge pump design will be integrated at the top level with other blocks such as PFD, VCO, frequency divider and low pass filter for the system level PLL design. The practical applications of this includes RF wireless transceivers targeting applications such as WiFi, Bluetooth or 5G can have better PLL performance. Other than that, SERDES protocol chips that employ a PLL for timing purposes such as MIPI, SONET, USB, HDMI, PCI Express, Ethernet protocols can have accurate timing circuitry.

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